

DRUGS USED IN ALZHEIMER'S AND COGNITIVE DISORDERS AND THEIR MECHANISM OF ACTION.

Akbaraliyev is the son of Khojiakbar Shuhrat

Associate professor.

Qalandarov Qabil Suyarovich

Alfraganus University

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Abstract: As we mentioned in our previous articles, hundreds of medical experts around the world are looking for the origin of dementia and mental retardation diseases and ways to detect them in advance. We are talking about the drugs that prevent them.

Keywords: "Leqembi", lecanemab-irmb, FDA, ARIA, Eisai Inc, steroids, AD, cognitive, dementia, monoclonal antibodies.

When we talk about Alzheimer's disease, first of all, we will try to talk about its treatment and try to explain its essence. Let's dwell on the idea that Alzheimer's disease may come. When we always think about Alzheimer's disease, the USA passes before our eyes. Because once upon a time, even this disease was recorded in the history of America. Therefore, it is not an exaggeration to say that the research of American scientists in recent years is expected to be useful for the treatment of this disease. As a reason for this, we can take as an example the drug created by scientists in a new interpretation. The name of this drug is called "Leqembi". Let's talk about this newly created drug: Leqembi (lecanemab-irmb) is used to slow down the progression of Alzheimer's disease (AD) in people with mild cognitive impairment or mild dementia. Leqembi is not a cure for AD, but it can slow cognitive decline by about 27% over 18 months in most people with AD. Leqembi belongs to a class of drugs called monoclonal antibodies. Leqembi first received FDA approval on January 6, 2023 under the accelerated approval pathway. This has been extended to full approval on 06 July 2023.

Side effects of Leqembi, the most common side effects of Leqembi are:
infusion-related reactions, which can be serious;
headache;
swelling in areas of the brain, with or without small areas of bleeding on or near the surface of the brain (ARIA).

Label price:

The cost of Leqembi depends on your insurance coverage and eligibility for Leqembi Copay. For help determining coverage and financial assistance programs, see Eisai Patient Support. Medicare covers 80 percent of the cost of

Leqembi, but other costs, such as PET scans and follow-up MRI scans, may not be covered. Leqembi Companion is A website designed to support you during your treatment with useful tips and useful information about Leqembi infusion. You may have a question, How do I take Leqembi?

The vaccine is given by a healthcare provider through a needle inserted into a vein in your arm (intravenous (IV) infusion).

Leqembi is given every 2 weeks.

Each Leqembi infusion takes about 1 hour.

To reduce the risk of having an infusion-related reaction with Leqembi, you may take medications such as antihistamines, anti-inflammatory drugs, or steroids before your infusion. If these symptoms appear during the infusion of Leqembi, tell your doctor immediately:

fever

flu-like symptoms (chills, body aches, chills, and joint pain)

nausea

vomiting

dizziness or vertigo

a change in heart rate or a feeling of chest tightness

difficulty breathing or shortness of breath.

Of course, you may have a question, who and what company produces the drug Leqembi, the drug Leqembi is produced by: Eisai Inc.

In conclusion, we can say that even our drug "**Leqembi**", whose name has been highlighted, is not used for the full treatment of Alzheimer's disease. We hope that this disease will be included in the list of incurable diseases.

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